

EFFECT OF CARBON NANOTUBE DISPERSION ON THE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF POLYMERS

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SUMMARY

The effect of carbon nanotube (CNT) on the fracture toughness of polymers is modelled in this paper. Dispersion quality plays an important role on the toughness. Hence, a new systematic experimental procedure is set-up to quantify the degree of dispersion of the CNTs and to understand its role on the toughness of nano-modified resins.

Keywords: Carbon nanotube, fracture modelling, nanocomposite processing, carbon nanotube dispersion, multifunctional nanocomposites

INTRODUCTION

Recently, the effect of carbon nanotubes as the reinforcement of the matrix in composite materials has been studied [1]. These studies showed an increase in fracture toughness even at low-CNT content. CNT reinforced resins can increase the composite ductility through different toughening mechanisms such as CNT pull-out (i.e. CNT/matrix debonding), CNT bridging, and crack deviation. In this paper, the main toughening mechanism, i.e. CNT bridging, is modelled using Elastic Plastic Fracture Mechanics (EPFM). According to the model, several parameters should be considered to improve the fracture toughness. These parameters include the length, the diameter, the volume fraction, the degree of dispersion, and the alignment of CNTs. A systematic approach to verify the effect of CNT dispersion on the toughness of nano-modified polymer is the main focus of this paper.

FRACTURE TOUGHNESS MODELLING

The addition of CNTs to the resin has two main effects: increasing the elastic modulus of the neat resin [2], and introducing toughening mechanisms such as CNT bridging [3-5]. The most important types of CNT bridging, leading to the enhancement of the fracture toughness in nanocomposites, depends on the embedded length of CNTs in the resin. The bridging process could be either CNT pull-out or CNT rupture. In both bridging processes, the nanotube bridges the crack surfaces shielding the crack front from carrying the entire tensile load. Hence, CNT pull-out and rupture are responsible for the nonlinear stress-strain behaviour of modified resin systems. In this section, these two bridging mechanisms are modelled to verify the effect of CNTs as toughening filler of a brittle resin.

The contribution of the bridging effect can be calculated using the definition of the J-integral given by,

$$J = \int_{\Gamma} \left(w dy - T_i \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x} ds \right) \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

where w is the strain energy density, T_i are the components of the traction vector defined as the stresses acting normal to the contour, u_i are the displacement vector components, and ds is a length increment along the contour Γ .

Assuming that the CNTs are normal to the crack growth plane, there are two possible scenarios in a CNT bridging process. If the embedded length of a CNT, l , is equal or smaller than a critical length, $l_c/2$, the CNTs will pull-out, whereas for embedded length greater than the critical length, the nanotubes will rupture before pulling out [6]. This critical length is computed by a simple force balance and is given by,

$$\frac{l_c}{r} = \frac{\sigma_f}{\tau} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

where r is the nanotube radius, σ_f is the nanotube ultimate strength, and τ is the interfacial shear stress assumed to be constant.

To model the contribution of the pull-out process, for CNTs with volume fraction V_f and an average length L , we assume that nanotubes are embedded in the resin with an equal length l . Similar to the Dugdale-Barenblatt strip yield model [7], CNTs exert a traction force on the crack faces. Accordingly, for a relatively long bridging zone, the first term in the J contour integral vanishes as $dy=0$, and the contribution of the $J_{pull-out}$ for CNTs can be expressed as,

$$J_{pull-out} = \int_{\Gamma} \left(\sigma_{yy} \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x} ds \right) = 2 \int_0^{\rho} \sigma_{yy}(x) \left(\frac{\partial u_y(x)}{\partial x} dx \right) = V_f \int_0^l \left(\frac{2\tau l}{r} dl \right) = V_f \left(\frac{\tau l^2}{r} \right) \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

where ρ is the length of the pull-out zone, and $2u_y=l$ at the end of the pull-out zone.

When $l \geq l_c/2$, J_b is the energy release rate for the rupture of CNTs at the strain before rupture ($J_{rupture}$). Similar to the pull-out modelling, this contribution can be modelled as,

$$J_{rupture} = V_f \int_0^{u_{max}} \sigma_{yy}(u) du \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

where u_{max} can be approximated as, $u_{max} \approx L \times \epsilon_{max}$, where L is the CNT total length and ϵ_{max} is the CNT failure strain. It is assumed that the wall of the nanotube is detached from the resin, while the two ends are still attached. The value of $J_{rupture}$ is the area under the stress versus displacement curve for rupturing a CNT. Assuming a linear stress-strain curve for CNTs, this area can be approximated as $(\sigma_u \times L \times \epsilon_{max})/2$,

$$J_{rupture} = \frac{1}{2} (V_f \sigma_u L \epsilon_{max}) \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

An average J_b is calculated for nanotubes with uniform length L , when the embedded length varies. For $L \leq l_c$, all CNTs pull-out with no rupture. The total contribution of J_b is given by,

$$J_{pull-out} = V_f \frac{\int_0^{L/2} (\tau l^2 / r) dl}{L/2} = \frac{1}{12} V_f \left(\frac{\tau L^2}{r} \right) \quad \text{for } (L \leq l_c) \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

For $L \geq l_c$, assuming a very well dispersed modified resin, only $V_f \times l_c / L$ portion of the CNTs pull-out, and the rest of the CNTs ($V_f \times (1 - l_c / L)$) rupture. It should be noted that according to the value of l_c for CNTs, the pull-out portion of the nanotubes is very small. Hence, the total pull-out contribution is

$$J_{pull-out} = \frac{V_f l_c}{L} \frac{\int_0^{l_c/2} (\tau l^2 / r) dl}{l_c/2} = \frac{1}{12} V_f \frac{l_c}{L} \left(\frac{\tau l_c^2}{r} \right) \quad \text{for } (L \geq l_c) \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

and the nanotube rupture contribution is

$$J_{rupture} = \frac{1}{2} V_f \left(1 - \frac{l_c}{L} \right) \sigma_u L \mathcal{E}_{max} \quad \text{for } (L \geq l_c) \quad \text{Equation 8}$$

The total contribution of CNT bridging for the ($L \geq l_c$) is the sum of Eqs. 7 and 8.

These equations show that for an average length of CNTs from zero to the critical length, the contribution of fibre pull-out is proportional to L^2 , and for longer CNTs, it is inversely proportional to L . However, for the latter, nanotube rupture increases the total bridging effect.

Using the bridging model, the contribution of CNT bridging to the toughening effect of CNTs in brittle resins is approximated based on the experimental results from literature. The CNT critical length is calculated from values for the interfacial shear bonding and tensile strength of nanotubes. Barber et al. [8] measured a nanotube-polymer interfacial strength of 47 MPa from experiments of MWCNT pull-out from a cured polyethylene-butane matrix. The CNTs radius is assumed to be 7 (nm), $\tau = 47$ (MPa), $\sigma_{u(CNT)} = 40$ (GPa), and elongation to fracture of CNTs is assumed to be 10%.

Figure 1 shows the contribution of the bridging effect on the fracture toughness of a CNT-modified resin in Mode-I for perfectly aligned and randomly dispersed CNTs. In order to adapt the CNT bridging model, i.e. Eqs. 6 – 8, for the random alignment of CNTs, the contribution of the J_b is multiplied by the probability of having CNTs normal to the crack propagation plane. We assume that a nanotube with a minimum 50° angle with respect to the crack growth plane contributes fully to the bridging process. To evaluate the probability, a sphere with diameter equal to the length of a CNT is considered in 3D space. The possibility of having minimum 50° angle with respect to the crack growth plane is the area of a spherical cap with the height of $l/2 \times (1 - \sin(50))$ divided by the area of a half sphere with diameter l . This ratio can be calculated as,

$$\text{Probability} = \frac{2\pi(l/2)^2(1 - \sin(50))}{2\pi(l/2)^2} = 1 - \sin(50) = 0.23 \quad \text{Equation 9}$$

Thus from Eq. 9, only 23% of CNTs will contribute to the bridging process, hence, according to the uniform length of the nanotubes, L , Eqs. 6 - 8 should be multiplied by 23%. A typical value for the fracture toughness of epoxy resin at crack initiation is around 200 (J/m²). Therefore, based on theory, CNTs have the potential to improve the fracture toughness of brittle resins in mode-I fracture.

Figure 1: Effect of CNT-bridging on the fracture toughness of brittle resins as a function of the average length of CNTs for a Single Walled CNT

According to the results presented in this section and also the effect of alignment of CNTs, the only way to improve the fracture toughness of nanocomposites is to incorporate long CNTs with high volume fraction into the resin system and to align them perpendicular to the fracture growth surface. This resin modification process results in CNT bridging and rupture rather than pull-out. Figure 2 depicts the steps to improve the fracture toughness of CNT-modified resins.

Figure 2: Steps to improve the toughness of brittle polymers by incorporating CNTs

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Materials

The polymer used in this study was a standard aerospace grade epoxy, Araldite[®] MY0510 epoxy, supplied by Huntsman. This epoxy was used with two different types

of hardener as the curing agent: 1. Aradur[®] HY976-1 which is 4, 4-Diaminodiphenyl Sulphone (refer to as DDS), and 2. Aradur[®] 5200 which is a non-MDA based aromatic diamine (refer to as Aradur). The former is a powder type hardener and in 19 min at 180°C gels the MY0510. The latter however, is a liquid hardener and the gel time is 9 min at 180°C.

The nanotubes used in this work were Single Walled Carbon Nanotube (SWNT) supplied by the National Research Council Canada's Steacie Institute for Molecular Sciences (NRC-SIMS) located in Ottawa, Ontario, Canada. The nanotubes were processed using two different techniques a highly efficient laser-oven technique, and a plasma enhanced chemical vapour deposition. The details of the production of the former technique are given by Kingston et al. [9]. The former production technique resulted in SWNT purity level of about 80 wt.% and metal catalyst contamination of under 6 wt.%. The remaining composition was made up of impurities such as amorphous and graphitic carbon particles.

Specimen preparation

The unfunctionalized SWNTs (0.3 wt.%) were mixed with MY0510 epoxy at NRC-SIMS. In order to facilitate the mixing of the nanotubes in the resin, the MY0510 was first dissolved in the organic solvent, Tetrahydrofuran (THF). The solution was then mixed under nitrogen with the epoxy monomer by energetic shaking, bath sonication and finally using a high-shear mixer. The THF was removed by placing the THF/SWNT/MY0510 under vacuum at 80°C for about 2.5 hours until all the solvent has evaporated. Once these were prepared, the neat MY0510, and unfunctionalized SWNT/MY0510 and the hardeners were shipped separately. For the DDS system, the hardener to resin ratio is 60:100, and for the Aradur 5200 is 35:100.

Fracture toughness samples were prepared according to the standard test method for measurement of fracture toughness of polymer materials, ASTM D 5045 – 91. Single Edge Notch Bending test was chosen for 3-point bending test and the dimensions of the samples were chosen as 20(mm)×4(mm)×2(mm) with the notch depth of 2(mm) and a span of 16(mm). A mould was designed to produce 10 fracture toughness testing samples simultaneously. The flow of the resin must be minimized to reduce the possibility of void formation in the samples. Hence, mould casting was chosen to produce the low-CNT-content samples. The conceptual design of the mould is depicted in Figure 3. The mould contained two Teflon inserts where the resin is poured. Having channels on the top Teflon insert allowed for easier sample demoulding. Aluminum components were used to close and seal the mould. Pressure at 6 bars was applied on one end of the channels forcing the resin into the channels and removing any possible voids. For the DDS system the cure cycle was 1 hour at 100°C, 2 hours at 135°C and 2 hours at 180°C. For the mixture with Aradur, the cure cycle was 2 hours at 150°C and then 2 hours at 180°C.

CNT dispersion analysis test setup

One of the key parameters that affect the mechanical properties of polymer CNT composites is the CNT dispersion quality in the samples. A Linkam Examina Dynamic hot-stage was used to monitor the CNT dispersion quality during the curing process.

The effect of the two different hardeners on CNT dispersion degradation up to the gelation point was verified with the hot-stage.

Figure 3: Mould conceptual design (left), and in use for making fracture samples (right); the channels on the top Teflon part set the size of the samples

Fracture test setup

The fracture toughness samples were tested with a 3-point bending fixture in order to: verify the bridging model presented in the first section of this paper and to validate the effect of CNT dispersion quality on toughness. A 100lb Fullam tensile fixture was used to perform the tests under an Optical Microscope (Olympus BX-51M). The size of the initial crack length was measured and noted for each specimen prior to the test under the OM. Figure 4 shows the setup.

Figure 4: Fullam tensile test fixture, and the initial crack under optical microscope

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

CNT dispersion analysis

During the sample preparation, the effect of elevated temperature on the deterioration of the CNT dispersion quality was noticed. A well dispersed sample is highly required to process well dispersed nanocomposite structures. In the case of fracture toughness, poor dispersion may result in stress concentration areas, which reduces the strength and

fracture toughness value of the CNT modified resin compared to the neat resin. To verify the effect of temperature on dispersion degradation prior to the gelation point of the resin mixtures, a systematic series of tests was used.

Figure 5 shows the CNT dispersion stability analysis for a 0.3% wt % SWNT in the MY0510 epoxy system. The state of the CNT dispersion at 100× magnifications at room temperature (25 °C) was compared to 180 °C.

Figure 5: CNT dispersion stability analysis using the Linkam hot-stage setup

At 25 °C, the nanotubes were well dispersed, however, when the temperature was increased to 180 °C, the nanotubes started to agglomerates and the CNT dispersion quality deteriorated significantly. The only sample that was relatively stable at 180 °C was the Laser SWNTs in the MY0510 epoxy with the Aradur hardener. The agglomeration observed for the other cases was mainly caused by a combination of lower resin viscosity, thermal expansion and chemical curing of the mixture. The

temperature ramp rate had no significant effect on the CNT dispersion degradation by comparing the two DDS samples in Figure 5. Thus based on the CNT dispersion analysis shown, the laser SWNT MY0510 epoxy system cured with Aradur is expected to have better fracture toughness.

Fracture toughness test results

The results of the fracture tests (Figure 6) show that the DDS hardener led to higher fracture toughness compared to Aradur. This was expected as DDS was recommended by the manufacturer as the optimum curing agent for the MY0510 epoxy system. For the Aradur system, it should be noted that the standard deviation from the mean value for the neat MY0510 was larger. In general, the addition of carbon nanotube to the MY0510/DDS system deteriorated the fracture toughness values. However, for the MY0510/Aradur, the laser SWNTs slightly improved toughness by 8%. This result is consistent with the CNT dispersion stability analysis results. The laser SWNT dispersion with the Aradur as hardener was more stable compared to the other samples. Similarly, the reduction in fracture toughness, for the plasma SWNT with Aradur and also the DDS system can be interpreted as a result of poor CNT dispersion quality of the nanotubes (Figure 5).

Figure 6: Fracture toughness test results, MY0510 epoxy system with SWNT; Aradur (light grey columns, left), and DDS (dark grey columns, right)

The increase in the SWNT weight fraction with the MY0510/DDS decreased the fracture toughness. This result is clearly in contradiction with the modelling work presented in the previous section. The fracture toughness model does not account for the dispersion degradation as the CNT content increases. Poor CNT dispersion quality resulted in stress concentration areas on the crack growth plane and consequently material failure at much lower loads. This effect must be accounted for in future toughness model developments.

The cross section of the fractures samples were studied under an optical microscope (Figure 7). The fractured surface was rougher for MY0510/DDS leading to higher fracture toughness values. However, for MY0510/Aradur, the CNT dispersion on the

crack growth plane was clearly more uniform. These images are in agreement with the results from the CNT dispersion analysis.

Figure 7: Fracture surface of the tested samples, arrows show the nanotube aggregated regions

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the CNT bridging model presented in this paper, aligning long (~50 μm) carbon nanotubes perpendicular to the crack growth plane has great potential to enhance the toughness of brittle polymers. This improvement is due to the toughening mechanisms, mainly CNT bridging, that these nano particles introduce inside a polymer. On the other hand, for low nanotube fractions (lower than 2%) randomly dispersed, the modelling shows that no significant enhancement in toughness can be achieved. Therefore, toughness enhancement with CNTs is bounded by the limitations and challenges in the processing of the CNT polymer mixture.

To better understand these limitations and challenges, a systematic approach was used to verify the effect of degree of CNT dispersion on the fracture toughness. A CNT dispersion stability analysis at elevated temperature was employed to identify the best CNT-hardener-epoxy formulation. The laser SWNTs with Aradur as the hardener were more stable during the curing process in the MY0510 epoxy system.

The fracture toughness experimental results confirmed the importance of the CNT dispersion stability quantification. The most stable formulation (MY0510, Aradur, Laser SWNT) was the only system that led to the improvement of fracture toughness. Even though the toughness enhancement was not as high as what is expected from the modelling, the enhancement due to the dispersion quality improvement was considerable.

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References

- [1] Thostenson, E. T., and Chou, T.-W., 2006, "Processing-Structure-Multi-Functional Property Relationship in Carbon Nanotube/Epoxy Composites," *Carbon*, 44(14), pp. 3022-3029.
- [2] Ashrafi, B., and Hubert, P., 2006, "Modeling the Elastic Properties of Carbon Nanotube Array/Polymer Composites," *Composites Science and Technology*, 66(3-4), pp. 387-396.
- [3] Fiedler, B., Gojny, F. H., Wichmann, M. H. G., Nolte, M. C. M., and Schulte, K., 2006, "Fundamental Aspects of Nano-Reinforced Composites," *Composites Science and Technology*, 66(16), pp. 3115-3125.
- [4] Gojny, F. H., Wichmann, M. H. G., Fiedler, B., and Schulte, K., 2005, "Influence of Different Carbon Nanotubes on the Mechanical Properties of Epoxy Matrix Composites - a Comparative Study," *Composites Science and Technology*, 65(15-16), pp. 2300-2313.
- [5] Gojny, F. H., Wichmann, M. H. G., Kopke, U., Fiedler, B., and Schulte, K., 2004, "Carbon Nanotube-Reinforced Epoxy-Composites: Enhanced Stiffness and Fracture Toughness at Low Nanotube Content," *Composites Science and Technology*, 64(15), pp. 2363-2371.
- [6] Kelly, A., 1970, "Interface Effects and the Work of Fracture of a Fibrous Composite," *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series A, Mathematical and Physical Sciences*, 319(1536), pp. 95-116.
- [7] Anderson, T. L., 1994, *Fracture Mechanics: Fundamentals and Applications*, CRC Press, Florida.
- [8] Barber, A. H., Cohen, S. R., and Wagner, H. D., 2003, "Measurement of Carbon Nanotube-Polymer Interfacial Strength," *Applied Physics Letters*, 82(23), pp. 4140-4142.
- [9] Kingston, C. T., Jakubek, Z. J., Denommee, S., and Simard, B., 2004, "Efficient Laser Synthesis of Single-Walled Carbon Nanotubes through Laser Heating of the Condensing Vaporization Plume," *Carbon*, 42(8-9), pp. 1657-1664.